

Exploring Generation Z's Expectations and Preferences Regarding Key Motivational Factors with Special Reference to Teaching Professionals

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Abstract

In the evolving landscape of the education sector, Generation Z is emerging as a crucial component of the workforce. Understanding what motivates this generation is imperative for academic institutions striving to retain young talent and ensure long-term engagement. This research explores the relative impact of materialistic and non-materialistic motivational factors on Generation Z teaching professionals. Drawing on a sample of 120 respondents through a structured questionnaire, this study employs descriptive analysis to interpret data. Findings highlight that while financial rewards remain foundational, non-materialistic aspects such as recognition, work-life balance and professional autonomy plays a vital role in motivating Gen Z faculty members. The study contributes to the literature of offering insights that could guide institutions in designing comprehensive motivational strategies that align with Gen Z expectations.

Key Words: Generation Z, Motivational Factors, Teaching, Materialistic, Non-Materialistic

INTRODUCTION

Generation Z, also referred to as the iGeneration or digital natives, comprises individuals born between 1997 and 2020, they accounted for over a quarter of the global population and have rapidly become an influential workforce segment. Unlike Millennials, Gen Z professionals exhibit distinct traits, they are pragmatic, values stability and demand meaningful engagement over superficial perks. The relationship with work is deeply influence by technology, real-time feedback and desire for continuous learning. In academic institutions, where intellectual contribution and interpersonal interactions are central, understanding the motivational drivers of Gen Z teaching professionals is both timely and essential.

With the retirement of Baby Boomers and the approaching exit of Generation X from active service, Generation Z and millennials are stepping into leadership and frontline roles. In this context, motivation -

particularly Taylor motivation is key to performance and retention. Previous generations may have prioritized job security and financial compensation, but Generation Z adds layers of complexity to the secretion seeking flexibility, autonomy and recognition.

Materialistic Motivation Factors:

Materialistic motivational factors are tangible rewards offered by organizations, primarily involving monetary compensation and financial benefits. These include:

1. **Salary and Monetary Compensation** – The basic fixed remuneration received by employees.
2. **Bonuses and Allowances** – Performance-based incentives
3. **Paid Holiday and Sick Leave** – Time-off policies that offer financial security.

4. **Medical Insurance** – Health benefits that support the well-being of employees.
5. **Professional Development Funding** – Financial Support for conferences, workshops and further education.
6. **Retirement Benefits (PF/ESI)** – Long-term financial planning aids.
7. **Grants and Research Funding** – Essential in academic settings for motivation and performance.

Materialistic rewards are often the first form of motivation assessed in any employment context. While essential, especially for economic security, they are often insufficient on their own to maintain high levels of engagement in the long run.

Non-Materialistic Motivation Factors:

Non-materialistic motivational factors are intangible benefits that enhance job satisfaction and emotional well-being. These include:

Recognition and Appreciation – Timely feedback and acknowledgement from superiors.

Work-life Balance – Flexibility in schedules and manageable workloads.

Professional Development Opportunities – Training, upskilling and career progression without direct financial incentives.

Autonomy in Decision-Making – Empowerment to make academic and professional decisions.

Collegial Environment – Positive relationships and teamwork opportunities.

Job Security and Defined Roles – A stable and transparent workplace.

Organizational Culture and Prestige – Sense of belonging and pride in the institution.

Such factors are instrumental in creating a motivating and supportive environment,

which is increasingly valued by Generation Z.

Generation Z:

Generation Z is a highly adaptable, innovative and technology-savvy generation. Their early exposure to the internet and social media has shaped their cognitive styles, communication preferences and workplace expectations. Key characteristics include:

Tech-Native and Digital Fluent:

Raised in the era of smartphones and cloud technology, Gen Z is comfortable with digital tools and expects workplaces to be equally adept.

Desire for Stability: Contrary to assumptions of restlessness, Gen Z seeks secure jobs with well-defined career paths.

Feedback-Oriented: They prefer continuous and real-time feedback over annual performance reviews.

Inclusivity and diversity: Gen Z values inclusion and expects their employers to reflect these ideals in policy and practice.

Work-Life Balance Advocates: Flexible working hours and the ability to manage personal time are top priorities.

Mission-Driven: They are more likely to stay in institutions that have meaningful goals and ethical practices.

Adaptability and Continuous Learners: They are quick to adapt and seek opportunities to grow and contribute.

Social Awareness: Many are driven by a sense of purpose, often preferring to work in organisations that contribute to societal good.

Understanding these traits is vital for designing motivational frameworks that align with their expectations.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

“Compared to Millennials, Generation Z place greater emphasis on

the level of basic salary” *Agnieszka Czerwinski et.al (2025)*.

“The researchers in the field of work motivation emphasize the importance of considering generational affiliation in better understanding the employees work motivation” *R.C. Lechler, M. Huemann (2024)*.

“Generation Z seamlessly expects immediate feedback and high rewards. They are also less likely to stay in institutions that don’t offer opportunities for growth and challenging work” - *Gruszczyńska-Malec G (2019)*.

“For Generation Z, work-life balance is the basis for functioning in professional life.” *Suvad Isakovic et.al (2021)*.

“Generation Z is a highly adaptable and goal-oriented generation, known for their quick learning and teamwork skills. Remote work is a standard expectation for them, and they prioritize high salaries and workplace flexibility. Growing up in the digital age, they are creative, socially aware, and value freedom. They reject toxic work environments and are drawn to companies with a meaningful mission. Proficient in languages, they excel in international settings and show a strong focus on innovation and social responsibility.” *Suvad Isakovic, Kanita Isakovic and Ajdin Isakovic (2021)*.

According to *Barford, I., & Hester, P. (2011)*, When it comes to work attitudes, Gen Z is motivated by materialistic extrinsic regulations.

Bielińska-Dusza (2022) highlighted that financial incentives are significantly more important than non-financial ones for Generation Z employees. This indicates a strong preference for material rewards over intrinsic motivators, underscoring the importance of competitive salaries, bonuses, and other tangible benefits when

designing motivation strategies for this cohort.

RESEARCH PROBLEM

In order to survive in the competitive field, management must ensure that its practices remain relevant and effective in meeting the expectations of the new generation workforce. As Generation Z becomes a significant part of the workforce, with an estimated 377 million people (30% to 35% of the total population), organizations are increasingly focused on finding ways to motivate Generation Z employees through both materialistic and non-materialistic means.

To add values to this concern, this study aims to explore the solution to the following research questions:

What factors motivate Generation Z to work in the particular institution?

What initiatives can educational institutions implement to motivate the Generation Z Workforce?

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this research are to:

Understand the expectations regarding motivational factors that influencing Generation Z at the workplace with special reference to the teaching professionals.

Establish the variables of materialistic and non-materialistic motivational factors in the field of teaching.

Explore various strategies that can be implemented to keep Generation Z motivated and sustained in the organization.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design:

This study employs a **descriptive-causal comparative research design** to examine the differences in motivational perceptions between genders within Generation Z teaching professionals. This

design helps identify whether statistically significant differences exist in responses based on gender.

Population and Sample:

The population includes Generation Z teaching professionals, specifically those born between 1997 and 2012. A purposive sampling technique was used to gather relevant data from 120 valid respondents, ensuring they fall within the required generational and occupational criteria.

Research Instrument:

The study utilized a structured questionnaire categorized into two key domains:

Materialistic Motivation Factors (MMFs) – e.g., salary, rewards, job security.

Non-Materialistic Motivation Factors (NMMFs) – e.g., recognition, autonomy, work-life balance.

Each item was evaluated on a **5-point Likert scale** ranging from 1 = *Not Important at All* to 5 = *Very Important*. Demographic information, including gender, was also collected for analysis.

Hypothesis Testing:

Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant difference between genders in their perception of materialistic and non-materialistic motivational factors.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): There is a significant difference between genders in their perception of materialistic and non-materialistic motivational factors.

Analytical Tools:

Data was analysed using JASP statistical software. The primary tool applied was:

Univariate ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) is a statistical test used to determine whether there are significant differences between the means of two or more independent groups on a single dependent variable.

Univariate ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) – to examine the influence of gender on each motivational factor individually.

Limitations of the Study:

The primary limitation of this study lies in the focus on gender alone as the independent variable. Other demographic variables like age, marital status, and years of experience were not considered, which may influence motivational preferences. Future studies should include broader variables for a more comprehensive understanding.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Univariate ANOVA Analysis

Materialistic Motivation Factors (MMFs)

MMF Code	Factor	F-value	p-value	Significance
MMF1	Remuneration	11.526	< .001	Significant
MMF2	Additional Income Opportunities	19.582	< .001	Significant
MMF3	Medical Insurance	1.964	0.164	Not Significant
MMF4	Criteria for Promotion	6.362	0.013	Significant
MMF5	Funding for Development	5.577	0.020	Significant
MMF6	PF/ESI – Security Benefits	0.633	0.428	Not Significant

Interpretation: Four out of six MMFs showed significant gender-based differences. Generation Z males and females differ in their emphasis on remuneration, additional income, promotions, and development funding.

Non-Materialistic Motivation Factors (NMMFs)

NMMF Code	Factor	F-value	p-value	Significance
NMMF1	Friendly Working Atmosphere	68.727	< .001	Significant
NMMF2	Low Work Stress	2.850	0.094	Not Significant
NMMF3	Professional Development Opportunities	0.209	0.649	Not Significant
NMMF4	Non-interference with Private Life	0.517	0.474	Not Significant
NMMF5	Fair Assessment of Work	5.198	0.025	Significant
NMMF6	Integration with Colleagues/Team	27.201	< .001	Significant
NMMF7	Independence in Decision Making	3.557	0.062	Marginal
NMMF8	Ergonomic Workplace	5.198	0.025	Significant
NMMF9	Location of Workplace	6.362	0.013	Significant
NMMF10	Image and Prestige of Institution	0.875	0.352	Not Significant
NMMF11	Defined Working Hours	3.920	0.050	Marginal
NMMF12	Job Security	11.526	< .001	Significant
NMMF13	Recognition from Higher Authorities	27.201	< .001	Significant
NMMF14	Opportunities to Represent in External Events	2.139	0.147	Not Significant

Interpretation: Significant gender-based differences were observed in areas like recognition, job security, team collaboration, and work environment. This indicates diverse motivational preferences across genders within Generation Z.

FINDINGS

Materialistic Motivation: Significant gender differences were observed in perceptions of remuneration, promotion criteria, funding for development, and additional income opportunities.

Non-Materialistic Motivation: Notable differences were found in recognition, team integration, job security, friendly work culture, and fair assessment.

Commonalities: Factors such as medical insurance, prestige of institution, and professional growth opportunities showed no significant variation across genders, suggesting common expectations among Generation Z educators in these areas.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the above findings, the following recommendations are proposed for educational institutions to retain Generation Z faculty members:

Tailor Recognition Programs: Design appreciation and recognition mechanisms that consider gender preferences and ensure visibility of efforts.

Promote Inclusive Teamwork: Foster collaborative team settings that appeal to both male and female faculty members, as team integration showed strong gender-based variation.

Transparent Promotion & Development Policies: Institutions should clarify career advancement criteria and support development initiatives equitably across gender lines.

Enhance Work Environment: Prioritize workplace ergonomics, job security, and positive institutional image to appeal to both genders effectively.

Empower Gender-Sensitive Motivation Strategy: Integrate findings into HR policies to create gender-responsive engagement and retention plans for young faculty.

CONCLUSIONS

The study reveals that gender significantly influences the motivational priorities of Generation Z teaching professionals, particularly in both materialistic and non-materialistic areas such as financial incentives, team collaboration, and recognition. Institutions aiming to recruit and retain this

generational cohort must customize their motivation strategies, taking into account gender-specific preferences. These insights will aid educational management in fostering an engaging, supportive, and inclusive environment that aligns with the expectations of the emerging workforce.

non-financial incentives, financial factors are much more important. *Journal of Human Resources Management Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5171/2022.637177>.

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